

Consumers' Preference towards Green Marketing - A Revolution against Pollution

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Abstract

In recent years of business environmental related problems play a crucial role in its marketing and also in the minds of consumers. All utmost all the countries around the world have worried to reduce pollution. As a result, all countries government step to take actions against pollution. Green marketing is also termed as environmental friendly marketing. It consists of number of activities like product process alteration, product alteration, package alteration and also advertising alteration. This study steps to identify the consumers’ preference towards the usage of green products. If companies, consumers and government realise their responsibility, the green environment can easily attain within a short period.

Keywords: Green Marketing, Eco-friendly, Green products, consumers’ preference,

Introduction

In recent years of business environmental related problems play a crucial role in its marketing and also in the minds of consumers. All utmost all the countries around the world have worried to reduce pollution. As a result, all countries government step to take actions against pollution. As a part of these business have started to restructure their product process in order to address these issues of new worries of the society. In older days, marketing process involves to satisfy the needs of consumers by selling products and services at reasonable prices. Green marketing is nothing but to define the term green and also improving and selling products according to the willingness of consumers.

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As defined by Tapan K. Panda “Green or Environmental selling consists of all activities designed to come up with and facilitate any exchange supposed to satisfy human desires or needs such the satisfaction of those needs {and wants and desires and desires} happens with lowest harmful impact on natural environment”.

To attain the objective of green marketing the following are concerned by the business;

- Eliminate the waste
- Bringing out product alteration
- Alteration in production process
- Alteration in product packaging
- Modification in advertising
- Makes prices which reflect actual and environmental costs

Reasons for Use of Green Marketing

Earth has only limited resources, with that every human being has to attempt to satisfy their unlimited wants. There is wide argument as to whether the earth is a resource at man's disposal. In market societies wherever there's freedom of selection. Generally accepted that individuals and organisations have the right to attempt to have their wants satisfied. Every business facing problem of limited resources, they have to develop new products or another ways to satisfying unlimited wants within these resources. The concept of green marketing exhibits the ways to utilise the unlimited resources in order to satisfy the unlimited wants of the consumers. While satisfying the consumers' unlimited wants, individuals and also business reflects the achievement of organisation's goals.

There is a several suggested reasons for usage of green marketing, there as follows;

- Every business understood the environmental marketing as an opportunity to fulfil its goals.
- Every business has believe that they have more social responsibilities.
- Government is forcing all the business/organisation to become environment friendly
- Competitors influence other business people to follow and develop their environment as environment friendly.
- Green marketing involves the alternative ways to reduce the waste and also optimum utilisation of limited resources, because of that the firms interested to follow environment friendly business in order to reduce high cost.
- Availability of opportunities for business growth
- Considering the future, it will be must in future business

Benefits of Green Marketing

In recent scenario, consumers are becoming more and more conscious regarding the environmental issues and socially responsible. Hence, most of the companies also perceived and become responsible to consumers hope for environmental friendly products or impartial products. Many business want to have some benefits to move towards green marketing. The following are the benefits can avail every company if move towards the green concept;

- Green concept warrants long term growth with profitability
- In long term, it helps to save money though its initial cost is more
- Green marketing paves the way to access new markets and also helps organisations enjoy the advantage of competitive.
- It helps to create a loyal employees for an organisation by making them to feel proud and responsible to be working for environment friendly organisation.

Challenges in Green Marketing

Though green marketing provides many benefits to an organisation, there is some difficulties in implementation of this concept. The following are the challenges which are facing by the organisation while go green;

- Currently there is no bench marking that is standardization and regulatory authorities to identify and certify the products as green.
- There is a lack of awareness about green marketing among the maximum of consumers particularly rural.
- Green marketing is a new concept, it takes long period to start to gain. The investors have to wait patience. It reflects the organisation share price.
- It is difficult to satisfy the consumers if products are developed which is purely green in various aspects. This will leads green bias.

Review of Literature

Maheswari (2014) stepped to identify the awareness of green marketing and its influence of buying behavior of consumers – special reference to Madhya Pradesh, India. In order to analyse the level of perception means, co-efficient of variation and standard deviations were used. There is a greater increase in the usage of environment friendly products. She concluded that greener products in the Indian market is under exploitation by the marketers who are within consumer groups with pro-environmental values. **Sao (2014)** attempt to identify the concept of green marketing. In that he identified three important parts like green consumers, explores the various challenges and opportunities which are available for business. He also examined the current scenario of green marketing and the reasons induce the companies to adopt the green marketing. He concluded that green marketing will continue to grow for long term in terms of both practical and demand wise.

Scope of the Study

This study covers the consumers' preference towards environment friendly products. The primary data collected from the people who are residing in around Dindigul town. The people consists rural, urban and also semi urban. Due to limited time and cost the data collected by using convenient sampling method. Around 200 respondents were considered for collecting data.

Objectives of the Study

This study attempt to attain the following objectives;

- To know the concept of Green Marketing
- To identify the consumers' preference towards the usage of green products

Research Methodology

This study used both the primary and secondary data for the accomplishment of the objectives. In case of primary data questionnaire was framed and data collected by sing interview schedule. This study also used the secondary sources which are already published like books, journals, newspapers and websites, etc.

Data Interpretation

Table 6.1 Demographic Profile of Respondents (No. of Respondents 200)

Demographic Factors		No. of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Gender	Male	85	42.5
	Female	97	48.5
	Transgender	18	9
Total		200	100

Age(Years)	Below 30	58	29
	31-40	67	33.5
	41-50	57	28.5
	Above 50	18	9
	Total	200	100
Marital Status	Single	74	37
	Married	126	63
	Total	200	100
Educational Qualifications	Illiterate	19	9.5
	Upto HSC	73	36.5
	Graduate	82	41
	Professional	26	13
	Total	200	100
Dwelling Place	Rural	41	20.5
	Urban	113	56.5
	Semi-Urban	46	23
	Total	200	100

From the Table 6.1 it is clear that the demographic profile of around 200 defendants who are the sample to study their attitude towards green marketing. Totally the data collected from male, female and also from transgender. Among them most of the defendants are female that is 48.5%. This is because of they have more responsible regarding the welfare of their family. Maximum of the defendants are fits to the age group of 31 to 40 (33.5%), which means that most of the defendants are entered into the family responsibilities (married). It indicates the maximum number of defendants are married in status that is 63% compared with unmarried defendants. Though a fewer defendants are illiterate, extreme are completed their graduate 41%. The data collected the defendants from the urban areas like 56.5%.

Findings

It is found from the above interpretation, the maximum of the defendants are female, age group of 31 to 40, married in status, and graduates. Though these categories are more as compared with others, remaining also having their own opinion/attitude towards go green. Even they also want to register their opinion by answering the questions framed by the researcher.

Table 6.2 Consumers' attitude towards Green Marketing

S. No.	Statements	SA	A	N	DA	SDA
1	Deterioration of the environment is a serious issue and Green products can contribute in saving the environment	106	54	27	10	3
2	I prefer green products over non green products.	64	89	15	28	4
3	Manufacturing/Production of green products is totally environment friendly.	42	67	21	45	25

4	Environment deterioration is bound to happen and green products cannot help in protecting it.	26	41	13	91	29
5	Green products and non -green products are alike.	17	26	16	87	54
6	Manufacturing of green products must be highly subsidized so that more companies can enter into manufacturing of green products.	75	47	18	34	26
7	Green products are true to their environment friendly claims.	13	24	11	98	54
8	Using green products gives a sense of satisfaction.	54	61	31	29	25
9	I want to be a part of green movement by using green products.	68	83	11	17	21
10	I am doubtful about the working performance of green products.	91	73	14	10	12
11	I would agree to pay even extra price for environment friendly products to save our environment.	67	38	31	47	17
12	Claims of green products about health benefits are usually exaggerated.	51	84	16	36	13
13	State Governments should make rigorous efforts to promote manufacturing and marketing of green products.	84	72	14	18	12
14	Performance of green products justifies its price.	41	32	17	84	26
15	Paying premium price for green products is a mere wastage of money.	43	27	37	85	8

From the above Table 6.2, it can be identify the attitude of the 200 defendants towards go green. In recent days, most of the consumers aware environmental issues and also become more responsible. The above statements reveal that the attitude of the defendants regarding green marketing. Most of the consumers (53%) trust that the eco- friendly products protect the environment from pollution. There are 44.5% of consumers prefer to buy green products as compared with non -green products.

The consumers like 33.5% thing that the manufacturing process of green products also may be environmentally friendly. 45.5% of respondents feel that the green products will protect the environment and they disagree the pessimistic view. There are 43.5 % of respondents disagree that the eco-friendly and non-eco-friendly products are same. They (37.5%) also feel that government may provide project fund to attract more number of companies to manufacture the green products.

Some of the respondents (45.5%) are having a doubt regarding the working of green products. There are 33.5% defendants ready to pay higher cost to buy green products. The respondents of (42%) are feeling that the benefits get from both green and non-green products are same. The consumers (42%) are preferring the state government should take severe action towards green. The performance of the green products are not justified by its price that is the opinion of 42% of respondents. There are 42.5% defendants are satisfied with the price of green products.

Findings

It is found that the above statements explains the various features of green products and the consumers’ opinion about its implementation. Many of the consumers became socially responsible

and aware about the environmental problems. They want to make a movement against pollution by using green products/eco-friendly products. They also want to use green products which are healthier to both the personal and social. Though they prefer towards green products, many of the consumers have a doubt regarding its manufacturing process and its performance. They suggest the government to take steps to motivate both the individual and companies to go green by framing strict rules and regulations. The features of green products may be exaggerated as compared with non-green products to attract the consumers.

Conclusion

Green marketing is not a simple one to implement in a short period, it takes time to an effective working. But it is the right time to follow the concept of green marketing slowly. Definitely it will create a dramatic change in the environment. It is possible only if government follow severe rules and regulations since to green marketing is an important to protect our earth and country from pollution. In case of business, they have to convince the consumers to buy their products and also involve them to market their products. In case of consumers should realise the societal responsible and get movement against the pollution. They may ready to use green products but the question is whether all the green products are really a eco-friendly or not? The consumer may ready to give higher cost to buy a product whether it will satisfy their needs or not? Some of the companies use these situation for their products by exaggerate their products by window dressing.

The government should take a necessary steps to control the companies which are manufacturing the green products and also regulate the advertising and packing system of the manufacturers. Government should frame governing bodies to verify the standardisation of green products. The consumers also should take efforts to know the features of green products which they are going to buy. They don't stop their enthusiastic to use green products only in words, it makes as true. If companies, consumers and government realise their responsibility, the green environment can easily attain within a short period.

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